

www.bjisrd.com

Rainfed Soils of the Gissar Range and their Fertility

Koraev Aliyor Khasanovich

PhD, senior researcher, Institute of Soil science and agrochemical research. Tashkent city, Almazar district, Kamarniso street building 3

***Abstract:** The object of the study was virgin and rainfed brown, dark, typical and light serozem soils, developed on the western slopes of the Hissar range. We also provide the morphology and the contents of humus and nutritional elements in these soils.*

***Key words:** virgin soils, rainfed soils, brown, dark, typical and light serozem soils, carbonate, gypsum, humus, nutrients, composition.*

Introduction. The aim of the study is to develop scientific and practical solutions directed to determining properties, assessing the quality, as well as preserving and improving the fertility of rainfed soils developed in the mountainous and submountain areas of the Hissar range.

Rainfed crops in Uzbekistan are located on gray soils and brown soils in the area of piedmont plains and foothills and in a strip of mid-altitude mountains, thus forming a kind of high-altitude zone encircling the mountain ranges of Central Asia. The lower boundary of this zone is determined by the lack of moisture in the desert soils in contact with it due to the low amount of precipitation and high evaporation in the desert. Uzbekistan is characterized by a continental type of subtropical climate. Its peculiarity is large thermal resources with significant amplitudes of air temperatures both in the daily and annual cycles and a pronounced periodicity of precipitation, confined to the autumn - winter - spring period. The unevenness of moisture throughout the year and the rapid increase in temperature during the transition from spring to summer create a unique water-thermal regime of soils, which determines two main hydrothermal and biologically different phases of vegetation: mesothermic, corresponding to a humid, warm spring, and xerothermic, a hot, dry summer. Besides, there is a short mesothermic period in autumn, when precipitation begins to fall before the onset of negative temperatures. The development of vegetation in the spring occurs under optimal conditions of moisture and warmth and quickly reaches its climax. Ephemera and ephemeroïds are well adapted to the conditions of the Turanian climate. They manage to complete the full development cycle with flowering and fruiting during the short period of spring rains and stop growing with the onset of hot and dry summer. Vegetation growth is also observed in the autumn short mesotherm period. The

mesothermic period also coincides with the passage of all stages of development and the formation of the harvest of cereal grain crops on rainfed soil.

In connection with the establishment of the territory of Uzbekistan belonging to the dry subtropics, not only our ideas about the soils of the republic, but also our attitude towards them as a natural productive force must radically change [1, 2]. When developing rational agricultural technology on rainfed lands of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to use the experience of dry farming accumulated in arid subtropical countries.

The rainfed farming zone within the above boundaries belongs to the vertical zone region of the Turan soil-climatic province, located on gray soils in the arid climate zone. The above-discussed features of the arid climate determine the ephemeral nature of soil moisture in the gray soil belt with a non-flushing type of regime and a deep position of the groundwater level.

The soil cover of the lower part of the rainfed zone within the piedmont plain and foothills is represented by gray soils. These are very low-humus and highly calcareous soils poor in colloids. In their profile, differentiation into genetic horizons is observed in connection with humus accumulation, structuring and partial illuviation of carbonates of alkaline earth bases. These soils, confined to piedmont formations, are developed predominantly on loess-like loams. Gray soils are divided into light, typical and dark, replacing each other as they approach the mountains and the altitude of the area increases. The main differences between the named subtypes are due to the different humus content, the degree of soil eluviation from carbonates, and the thickness of the genetic horizons. Natural vegetation on light gray soils is usually of ephemeral formation; In spring, ephemeroids predominate - narrow-leaved sedge (*Carex pochystilis*) and bulbous bluegrass (*Poa bulbosa*), which die off in summer.

The foothill plain adjacent to the Gissar ridge on the territory of the Kashkadarya region. Light rainfed gray soils are common on the foothill wide-undulating plains of the Gissar ridge. Soil-forming rocks are loess-like loams [3].

In field studies, morphological methods and laboratory chemical soil analysis methods [4] were used.

Research results. The object of the study was virgin and rainfed brown, dark, typical and light serozem soils, developed on the western slopes of the Hissar range. Light sierozems are the lightest soils in terms of mechanical composition in these rainfed regions. They are also dominated by coarse dust particles. Along with this, a reduced content of silt particles is noted - 2 - 4% and, as an exception, 8 - 10%. In terms of mechanical composition, the soils are predominantly medium and light-loamy with a high content of coarse dust fractions (67.7-68.5%) and a low content of silty particles (2-10%), which is typical for loess-like loams.

The content of physical clay in the arable horizon is 31-32%. Based on the content of water-soluble salts, light gray soils belong to the category of salted soils. The percentage of dense residue from 0.09 in the upper horizon increases deeper than the field meter to 0.4 – 0.5; The nature of soil salinity is sulfate. The upper layer of soil is free of gypsum, but deeper than a meter its content can reach 1%. The light gray soils of the Kashkadarya okug are characterized by high carbonate content. The CO₂ content varies along the profile from 6.2 to 8.3%. The maximum of carbonates is in the arable or subarable horizon, the minimum is at the end of the first meter.

Light gray soils are poor in organic matter. The tillage horizon contains from 0.78 to 0.80%, in the second half meter - 0.17 - 0.22%. Humus reserves in a meter thickness are 62 - 71 t/ha, which is significantly less than in analogues in other rainfed regions. The arable horizon usually contains 0.06 -

0.07% and within the second meter - 0.018 - 0.024% of nitrogen. Its reserves are minimal - up to 2 t/ha in the arable layer and up to 6 t/ha in a meter thick layer. The ratio of carbon to nitrogen is narrow - from 6 to 7 with maximum values in the upper horizons.

The content of gross phosphorus is also insignificant with a uniform distribution throughout the profile. Accordingly, its reserves are relatively small - 3 - 4 t/ha for the arable layer and 15 t/ha for a meter thick layer. In contrast to the soils of higher zones, light gray soils contain slightly more mobile phosphoric acid. In the arable horizon, its amount varies (from 15 to 16 mg/kg) depending on the degree of cultivation and the manifestation of erosion processes. There is especially a lot of mobile phosphorus in fertilized soils. Below 20–25 cm its quantity gradually decreases. The reserves of available phosphorus range on average from 36 to 38 kg/ha in the tillage layer and from 126 to 137 kg/ha in a meter thickness. The amount of phosphorus reserves is greatly influenced by agricultural practices. The content of gross potassium in light gray soils ranges from 1.4 to 1.6% with a maximum in the upper horizons. In terms of reserves of this element, light gray soils both in the arable layer (34 - 39 t/ha) and in the meter thick layer (150 - 163 t/ha) are almost no different from their analogues. In terms of the content of mobile potassium in the tillage horizon, they are predominantly classified as moderately rich. With depth, its amount gradually decreases and within the second meter it is 62 – 70 mg/kg. Reserves of mobile potassium – 408 – 475 kg/ha in the arable layer; in a meter thickness they increase to 1648 – 1829 kg/ha. It has been established that the absorption capacity of light gray soils, due to their light mechanical composition and poverty in organic matter and colloids, is low - 12 - 15 mg equivalent per 100 g of soil. The upper horizons are characterized by maximum capacity. Among the absorbed cations, calcium predominates - 54–64% of the amount of absorbed bases. Magnesium is much less - from 31 to 40%. Calcium dominates in all horizons, including rock. Potassium and sodium account for 4%. At the same time, the amount of potassium closer to the surface increases, and sodium decreases.

Conclusions. Among rainfed lands, light gray soils are the lowest in productivity. Therefore, the expansion of rainfed crops in the belt of light gray soils is completely futile, especially since the territory is classified as lacking precipitation. When plowing sierozems for rainfed crops, the established processes of sierozem formation are disrupted, in particular the supply and mineralization of plant residues, which leads to the depletion of soils in organic matter. As a result of field and laboratory studies, degradation of the region's soil cover was revealed. With the increase in the degree of erosion, the content and reserves of humus, reserves of nutrients, the amount of physical clay decreased, the structure worsened and the amount of moisture in the soil decreased. The deterioration of water-physical properties, nutrient and water regimes in eroded dry land sierozems led to a decrease in the overall productivity of agricultural lands, and a decrease in the yield on slightly and moderately eroded soils in relation to uneroded ones.

Literature

1. Koraev A.Kh. Current state of rainfed typical gray soils of the Gissar Range // Journal. Scientific review. Biological Sciences. Russian Federation. Russian Academy of Natural Sciences. – Moscow, 2018. No. 2 – P. 12 – 17.4.
2. Abdurakhmonov N.Y and R.K. Kuziev. Properties of Non – Irrigated Soils of Uzbekistan. //The Alberta Soil Science Workshop. Alberta Soil Science Foundation, (www.Soilsworkshop.ab.ca) February 18-20, 2003. Edmonton, Alberta, Canada.
3. Ismonov A.J., Abdurakhmonov N.Yu., Koraev A.Kh. Soil characteristics of the rainfed land fund of the Kashkadarya region // Current state and prospects for the development of reclamation soil

science: Materials of the international conference dedicated to the 100 th anniversary of V.M. Borovsky. – Almaty, 2009. – P. 77 – 78.

4. Rozanov B.G. Soil morphology. - M.: Academic project, 2004. - 432 p.